

THE NATURE AND IMPORTANCE OF VISUAL ARTS

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Abstract: This article describes in detail the essence and importance of visual art, the nature and content of teaching visual art at school, art is the expression of events in nature and society in artistic images, and the positive and most important feature of art.

Key words: visual art, painting art, creative imagination, pictorial image.

INTRODUCTION

Fine art is one of the oldest and most widespread types of art. In fact, there are many types of art. There are also other types of art such as fiction, music, visual arts, theater, cinema, choreography, architecture, applied decoration. Usually, the art that reflects the real existence in pictorial images, forms on a spatial dimension or plane is called visual art. Colors are also taken somewhat conditionally, however, it should give a true picture of existence. Monumental painting has a certain decorative function in architecture, so it is sometimes called monumental-decorative painting.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY:

The concept of fine art has a wide meaning. Until the 19th century, architecture, sculpture and painting were considered types of visual arts. At the end of the century, graphics became one of the most important and current types of visual arts. In the last 20 years, the type of art, like design, has found its place.

The art of painting is attractive and interesting, and requires a certain preparation from the student not only in mastering it, but also in being able to perceive it. Painting works are further divided into monumental, easel and decorative turian according to their function and method of development. Monumental paintings are closely related to architecture, and these types of works have an independent meaning and they depict important events from the life of society. Such works are usually intended to be viewed from a long distance and depict images as generalized as possible.

The science of fine art teaching methodology, the science of pedagogy, which determines the content, tasks and methods of teaching students to fine art, the purpose of education and upbringing. It is a field that organizes an effective educational process based on its tasks and researches its forms and ways.

Visual art classes in general education schools are considered to be the main means of learning aesthetic education, art and culture, history of Uzbek art, and are of great importance in educating students to become spiritually mature. In fine art classes, students learn the basics of scientific knowledge, master existence, which has an effective effect on their ideological, mental, moral, and aesthetic education.

RESULTS:

In the educational process of the visual art subject, the task of learning to apply the knowledge and skills given to students in life, marriage and other activities is set. However, according to the nature and content of teaching visual arts at school, it is possible to apply the theoretical knowledge and skills given in each lesson of this subject in practice in this lesson itself. Because in visual art classes, scientific and practical information, concepts, and instructions are given about the objects and events to be drawn and how to draw and describe them. Then practical work on the theoretical knowledge given in this lesson will begin.

In fine arts classes, students study the processes of drawing, color science, color image, graphics, design, and modeling depending on the object itself. Composition, compositional vision and compositional thinking are important factors in learning these processes. That is why visual art classes teach first of all how to draw and find a compositional solution to an object or situation. Composition and compositional thinking skills are important not only in fine arts classes, but also in human life.

The positive and main feature of art is that, unlike science, it expresses events not in concepts, but in forms perceived by intuition and feeling, in typical artistic images. Art fully expresses the good intentions of mankind, their dreams and hopes. Therefore, as much as our nation respects and respects its art, the nations of the world look at Uzbek art with the same sincerity and respect.

DISCUSSION:

Visual art classes are of particular importance in developing students' spiritual outlook and ideological beliefs. It develops the ability to think, visual memory, creative imagination, artistic taste, and aesthetic feeling. Each type of visual art classes taught at the school helps the growth of students' creative abilities, the improvement of their worldview, that is, it improves the personality in all aspects.

Art is the expression of events in nature and society in artistic images. Art reflects the general state of the material world, as well as its formation, and serves as a powerful factor in political, moral, and artistic education of a person. Art is divided into such types as fine art, architecture, literature, music, circus, theater, cinema, radio and television, according to the way of expressing reality, character, and essence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that all types of visual arts are very close to each other and have a number of similarities. But each of them has its own painting styles and techniques. If the content, character and all other features of the image are expressed through paints, it is called painting art. In this type of fine art, the artist describes his inner experiences through colors, skillfully shows the infinity of space, the color and materiality of things in it. For example, if red and black colors show tragedy, light blue and green colors can depict calm and peaceful situations.

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